

D6.4

2ND ANNUAL REPORT ON COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

V0.2

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ABBREVIATIONS

C, D & E: Communication, dissemination, and exploitation

HEU: Horizon Europe

KER: Key Exploitable Result

MCO: EHPA Manufacturers Committee

PUSH2HEAT: Pushing forward the market potential and business models of waste heat valorisation by full-scale demonstration of next-gen heat upgrade technologies in various industrial contexts.

WPs: Work Packages

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1. Introduction

This deliverable (D6.4) intends to collect and present all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out during months 13 and 24 of the project. This way spotlighting all the efforts dedicated to raising awareness, promoting the PUSH2HEAT project and its related results, and knowledge generated within and beyond the project, as described in D6.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy.

This is the second of four reports that will be also prepared on M36, M48. Initial report was prepared in M12.

2. Objectives

The annual report on communication, dissemination and exploitation aims to provide a clear overview of how all the communication channels and activities have worked together to increase the outreach of the project.

EHPA, as the Work Package leader of PUSH2HEAT's WP6 (Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation of Project results), and TECV as leader of T6.5 have overseen coordinating the implementation of the Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities with the cooperation, direct involvement, and support of the other Work Package leaders and all the project partners,

As described in D6.1, the approach to communication, dissemination and exploitation is different depending on the phase of its development. The activities gathered in this deliverable follow the approach of **Phase I**.

Phase I: Raise interest among key stakeholders aims at establishing a common project identity and raise awareness and interest regarding the project's expected results and impacts.

This report will be divided into three areas:

- **Communication activities:** focusing on the promotion of the project's activities and raising awareness of the benefits of heat upgrading technologies to a general audience, including decision-makers.
- **Dissemination activities:** focusing on the spread of the technical results of PUSH2HEAT to identified target groups and fostering collaborations with other related projects.
- **Exploitation activities:** focusing on ensuring the life-beyond-the-project of the PUSH2HEAT's Generated results.

3. Communication activities within the 2nd year

3.1. Visual identity

3.1.1. Project Promotional material

A series of factsheets briefly introducing the project's technologies were developed in M16. These have been circulated via social media and are accessible on the Push2Heat website. The factsheets can be found [here](#).

Figure 1: Factsheets

3.2 Website

The [Push2Heat website](#) was developed by EHPA in the early stages of the project to serve as a central hub for all Push2Heat-related public information. It allows stakeholders and others to access the project's objectives, progress, deliverables, newsletters, webinars, and preliminary results at any time. The website undergoes frequent updates and improvements to align with the project's evolving requirements throughout its lifecycle and for two years after its completion.

Since October 2023 until 16th August 2024, it has garnered 14642 unique visitors, 19363 visits and 353565 hits

Table 1: Stats on website October 2023 - 16 August 2024

Month/Year	Unique Visitors	Number of Visits	Hits
October 2023	861	1290	23429
November 2023	869	1242	38455
December 2023	1143	1545	25145
January 2024	1390	1834	32774
February 2024	1744	2361	44544
March 2024	1706	2386	38785
April 2024	1169	1340	24582
May 2024	1625	2028	43817
June 2024	1877	2495	35772
July 2024	1527	1991	35094
16 August 2024	731	851	11168
Total	14642	19363	353565

3.3 Social Media Channels

[LinkedIn](#) and [X](#) (formerly Twitter) were established as the primary social media channels for disseminating the work of Push2Heat to relevant target groups at the start of the project.

The social media accounts have been consistently used to share posts related to project updates, news, relevant events and other topics of relevance, with these channels we aim to maintain an active online presence, keep stakeholders informed and engage in discussions regarding the project's themes.

Since the D6.2 1st Annual C, D and E activities report, and as of the 16th of August 2024 our LinkedIn following has grown by 330 followers (versus 310 followers in M12, as reflected in D6.2), with a total number of **640** followers, whereas our X following has seen an increase of 63 followers (versus 30 followers reflected in D6.2), with a total number of **93** followers.

A dedicated [YouTube channel](#) was established to serve as a repository for all PUSH2HEAT video content produced throughout the project's duration. As of 16th of August 2024, the channel has 6 videos: including the project organised webinars, the 1st promotional video and a video interview on the conference Anuga Food Tec.

Regardless, all videos from the project are also shared on [EHPA's youtube channel](#), as it has an interested audience already established and 763 subscribers as of 16th of August 2024, and some of their members are also groups the project is interested in engaging with.

3.3.1 Stats LinkedIn

Push2Heat

Overcoming the barriers of the deployment of heat pump technologies for heat upgrading in the industrial sector

Industrial Machinery Manufacturing · 640 followers · 51-200 employees

Figure 2: Push2Heat LinkedIn profile header

Table 2: Stats Push2Heat LinkedIn

Number of followers until 16th of August 2024	640
Number of Post Published by Push2heat in the period covered by the 2nd annual C, D, E activities report (until 16th of August 2024)	31
Total impressions during the period covered by the 2nd annual C, D, E activities report (until 16th of August 2024)	23696
Total Clicks during the period covered by the 2nd annual C,D, E activities report (until 16th of August 2024)	2469

3.3.2 Stats X

Figure 3: Push2Heat X Profile

Table 3: Stats Push2Heat X

Number of followers until 16 August 2024	93
Number of Post Published by Push2heat on the period covered by the 2 nd annual C, D, E activities report (until August 16 th 2024)	39

3.4 E-Newsletter

The PUSH2HEAT newsletter was created to provide updated information about the project to relevant key stakeholders, gathered within the project's Stakeholder Network. During this 2nd year of activities, two e-newsletters were sent: The first was sent in **November 2023** (Available [here](#)) to 287 contacts and the third edition, in **March 2024** (Available [here](#)) to 368 contacts.

A 4th newsletter is set to be sent early October 2024. (M25)

3.4.1 Stakeholder Network

The stakeholder Network is an evolving community that has been progressively developed throughout the first months of the project. Its purpose is to bring together stakeholders who have

expressed interest in staying informed about PUSH2HEAT's activities. The initial list was formed by leveraging the contacts within the Project Consortium partner networks, with individuals who had shown interest in receiving updates about the project. Additional members have been added to the network through two main channels:

- The registration forms available on the PUSH2HEAT website, which is recurrently promoted through the project's social media accounts
- The participation in the PUSH2HEAT webinars, during which attendees had the opportunity to indicate their interest in joining the Stakeholder Network.

As of 16th of August 2024 the stakeholder network has 587 members.

3.5 Promotional videos

In M13, a promotional animation video was released to disseminate the purpose and goals of the PUSH2Heat project to a broader audience. The objective was to elevate awareness and foster interest in the initiative. The video, accessible [here](#), has garnered 6500 views.

Figure 4: stills from promotional video

3.6 Press releases and news

Between M13 and M24, 4 news articles have been published on the partner's websites.

Table 4: Press releases and news articles

EHPA	<u>Don't waste your energy! How heat pumps reuse waste heat in industry</u>	16 November 2023
POLIMI	<u>Ricercatori del dipartimento di energia al meeting europeo del progetto push2heat per l'innovazione nelle tecnologie di recupero di calore</u>	4 December 2023
EHPA	<u>Power to efficiency: unlocking industrial decarbonisation through heat pumps</u>	15 March 2024
EHPA	<u>Heat and Eat: heat pumps in the food and beverage industry</u>	11 June 2024

An article on the Newspaper FREIE PRESSE was published in May 2024. The article talks about the arrival of the SPH unit at Demo site 1 in Weissenborn. The article is available [here](#)

Figure 5: Article in Freie Presse

3.7 Scientific publications

A series of publications have been made by the Push2Heat Consortium over the course of the second year of the project. One of the publications is Open Access:

- Payá, J., Cazorla-Marín, A., Arpagaus, C., Corrales Ciganda, J. L., & Hassan, A. H. (2024). Low-pressure steam generation with concentrating solar energy and different heat upgrade technologies: Potential in the European industry. *Sustainability*, 16(5), 1733. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16051733>

Other publications have been made, not yet in Open Access:

- Payá Herrero, J., Hassan, A. H., & García, J. R. A. (2024, April 22-26). Aprovechamiento de calor residual mediante tecnología de bomba de calor: Caso de uso en planta de producción de mezclas asfálticas. In *XXII Congreso Ibero Latinoamericano del Asfalto (CILA)*. Granada, Spain.
- Payá Herrero, J., Hassan, A., & García, J. R. A. (2023, November 14-15). Aprovechamiento de calor residual y reducción de emisiones de efecto invernadero mediante tecnología de bomba de calor: Proyecto PUSH2HEAT-Caso de uso en planta de producción de mezclas asfálticas. In *XVIII Jornada Nacional de ASEFMA*. Madrid, Spain.
- Payá, J., Hassan, A. H., Gómez-Elegido, D., & Lucás-Alós, P. (2024, June 26-28). Viabilidad técnico-económica de distintas tecnologías de recuperación de calor en la industria agroalimentaria. In *XII Congreso Ibérico y X Congreso Iberoamericano de Ciencias y Técnicas del Frío*. Universitat Miguel Hernández, Elche, Spain.

- Payá, J., Hassan, A. H., Gómez-Elegido, D., & Sebastià, M. (2024, June 26-28). Análisis técnico-económico de distintas tecnologías de recuperación de calor en la industria papelera. In *XII Congreso Ibérico y X Congreso Iberoamericano de Ciencias y Técnicas del Frío*. Universitat Miguel Hernández, Elche, Spain.
- Alonso, L., & Corrales, J. L. (2024, January 23-24). Thermoeconomic analysis of waste heat upgraded steam production in the chemical industry using Type II absorption heat pumps. In *High-Temperature Heat Pump Symposium 2024*. Copenhagen, Denmark

The reason is that these materials have been presented at conferences, but we are currently still working on getting permission to publish them in Open Access.

4 Dissemination activities within the 2nd year

4.1 Events

Push2heat has been presented in 28 events related to the project scope over the 2nd year of the project. Below there is an overview of all events in which the project has been part of, some of them they have taken place in collaboration with other EU Projects.

Table 5: Events Push2Heat has participated in

Event	Date	Location	Type of participation	Number of participants/ audience reached	Partners involved
SEE ENERGY 2023	2-3 October 2023	Online	Presentation	350 participants	EHPA
EHPA's ICHP Working group	19 October 2023	Online	Presentation	20 participants	EHPA
Re-energising Europe: W4Res final conference in collaboration with W4RES project	25 October 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Poster	134 participants	EHPA
TCP on Heat Pumping Technologies	26 October 2023	Nuremberg, Belgium	Presentation	50 participants	TEC

(HPT TCP) by the IEA - National Experts meeting					
<u>Hochtemperatur- Wärmepumpen : Technologie und Anwendungen</u>	07 November 2023	Bern, Switzerland	Presentation	250 participants	OST
HPT TCP by IEA - National Experts Meeting	16 November 2023	Madrid, Spain	Presentation	20 participants	TEC
DKV Tagung 2023	23- 24 November 2023	Hannover, Germany	Presentation	100 Participants	SPH
<u>Paper and Beyond</u>	29 November 2023	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation	100 participants	SPH
<u>ENLIT Conference</u>	28-29 November 2023	Paris, France	Flyer distribution	400 participants and 30 audience members directly reached	EHPA
<u>The future is electrified, Get Ready!: International Conference on Industrial Heat Pumps</u>	29-30 November 2023	Prague, Czechia	Presentation	250 participants	EHPA,SPH , OST

<u>High Temperature Heat Pump Symposium</u>	23-24 January 2024	Copenhagen , Denmark	Presentations	400 participants	EHPA, OST, SPH, TEC, POLIMI
<u>Energy Fest 2024</u>	27 February 2024	Ghent, Belgium	Networking	25 audience members reached	EHPA
<u>ZF Power Summit</u>	29 February 2024	Bucharest, Romania	Presentation	150 participants	EHPA
<u>2024 high-temperature heat pump update</u>	6 March 2024	Online	Presentation	80 participants	OST
<u>Generación en Sitio. Una solución para la descarbonización de la industria</u>	12-14 March 2024	Online and Ciudad de México, México	Presentation	130 participants	EHPA
<u>Mostra Covegno Expo Comfort</u>	14-16 March 2024	Milan, Italy	Booth and flyers distribution	90000 participants	EHPA
<u>Steam Generating Heat Pump Webinar</u>	18 March 2024	Online	Presentations	460 participants	OST
<u>ANUGA FoodTEC</u>	18-22 March 2024	Cologne, Germany	Booth, video interview and flyer distribution	40000 Participants and 100 audience members reached out directly	EHPA

<u>New European Bauhaus Festival (exhibition)</u>	10-13 April 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Booth and flyers distribution	10000 participants	EHPA
EHPA General Assembly	16 April 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Flyers distribution and presentation	200 participants	EHPA
<u>Cooperation across SET Plan Implementation Working Groups (IWGs) Workshop</u>	24 April 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Presentation	25 participants	QPINCH
<u>Green Alternatives for Gas-Powered manufacturing processes</u>	24 April 2024	Genk, Belgium	Presentation	40 participants	VITO
<u>SET Plan – IWG Industry meeting</u>	5 June 2024	Namur, Belgium	Flyers distribution and networking	105 registered	EHPA
<u>Bridging Borders: Collaborative Solutions for European District Heating</u>	6 June 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Flyers and Networking	50 participants	EHPA
<u>EUSEW: European Sustainable Energy Week (Exhibition)</u>	11-13 June 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Booth and flyers distribution	10200 participants (total) – 2200 participants in Brussels	EHPA

EHPA's Manufacturers Committee (alongside <u>BETTED</u> Project)	20 June 2024	Brussels, Belgium and online	Presentation	50 participants	EHPA
EESF Toolkit 'Heat pump integration in the pulp and paper industry'	25 June 2024	Online	Presentation	Around 100 participants	TEC
<u>CYTEF 2024</u>	26-28 June 2024	Elche, Spain	Presentation and Poster	120 participants	UPV
<u>China Heat Pump Conference 2024</u>	27-30 August 2024	Shenzhen, China	Presentation		OST
<u>17th international congress on sorption heat pumps</u>	1-4 September 2024	Beijing, China	Presentation		TEC, TUB and POLIMI

Moreover, Push2Heat will be present at the EHPA's Heat Pump Forum on the 25th and 26th of September in Brussels, Belgium.

4.2 Webinars

Furthermore, Push2Heat has collaborated with other EU Funded projects and organisations in the organisation of 3 events from M13 to M24.

Table 6: Webinars organised by Push2Heat

<u>EU Perspectives on industrial heat pumps: unravelling non-technical barriers and opportunities</u>		
Date	14 November 2023	
Organisation	Push2Heat, SPIRIT & FEDARENE	
Data	Registrations: 153 Attendees: 93	Recording (402 views in August 16th 2024) News article
Background and aim of the webinar	This webinar was organised in the framework of SPIRIT and PUSH2HEAT, two Horizon Europe projects aiming to foster the decarbonisation of industry through high temperature heat pumps. The aim of the event is to explore non-technical barriers and opportunities within the heat pump sector, with a specific focus on Industrial Heat Pumps, from the perspective of different European countries.	
<u>Sustaining success of Industrial heat Pumps – a call to action!</u>		
Date	14 March 2024	
Organisation	Push2Heat, SPIRIT , SUSHEAT	
Data	Registrations: 224 Attendees: 170	Recording (719 views in August 16th 2024) News article

Background and aim of the webinar	<p>The aim of this webinar is to present the challenges but also the solutions that hide behind the integration of industrial heat pumps, not only from the perspective of the technology provider but also from the point of view of the end-user, i.e. all those industries that are “heat-pump ready” and can benefit from the installation of this technology to power their processes. To this end, after an overview of the most recent policy and technological developments that Europe has witnessed in the field of industrial heat pumps, you will hear one success story of industrial heat pump integration in the experience of the technology manufacturer and the end user.</p>	
<p><u>Heat and Eat: A matchmaking event for heat pumps and the food industry</u></p>		
Date	<p>28 May 2024</p>	
Organisation	<p>Push2Heat, SPIRIT, SUSHEAT</p>	
Data	<p>Registrations: 180 Attendees: 113</p>	<p>Recording (266 views in August 16th 2024) News article</p>
Background and aim of the webinar	<p>This event aimed to present the opportunities and benefits of high-temperature heat pumps when used in the food and beverage industry and to provide a space for heat pump & component manufacturers and food industry representatives to learn about the most relevant best practices in the sector and discuss opportunities for collaboration.</p> <p>The event was divided into two main parts: in the first hour the audience had the chance to hear about the potential of large-scale industrial heat pumps, the perspective of the food & beverage sectors on the decarbonisation of their processes and EU Funding opportunities supporting industrial CO2 reduction through this technology. The second hour of the event was focused on interaction among participants representing the food & beverage and heat pump industries. The discussions were organised around several round tables each of them focussing on a specific case study.</p>	

4.3 External Advisory Board

From M13 to M24 of the project, 2 new experts have joined the External Advisory Board. In October 2023, a meeting between the Push2Heat's Steering Committee and External Advisory Board was convened to introduce the project and its progress during the first year, laying the foundation for open collaboration. In June 2023, a second meeting between Push2Heat's Steering Committee and External Advisory took place, to update experts on the most relevant project news.

As part of this EAB collaboration, the project has been featured in the CEPInnovation's newsletter (CEPInnovation Newsletter, January 2024 [here](#)), disseminating updates to paper industry stakeholders. Additionally, the project was presented at the Paper and Beyond Conference held in Brussels in November 2023 and in EESF Toolkit "Heat Pump integration in the pulp and paper industry" In June 2024.

Table 7: Members of the External Advisory Board

Name of the Expert	Organisation
Annita Westenbroek	CEPI- Confederation of European Paper Industries
Dominic Laaf	ModellFabrik Papier
Elian Puscedu	Apricum
Bassam Badram	RI.SE
Rodrigo Álvarez	ASPAPPEL
Elena Troia	Industria Cartaria Pieretti
Sabine Höfel	Food Processing Initiative E.V

Exploitation activities within the 2nd year

5.1 Key Exploitable Results

After the workshop, an internal review of these KER was made in order to have a more consistent version, aiming always at a common understanding of each question, clarifying the innovation status of the KER or correcting, extending or completing descriptions where needed. As a result of this work, PUSH2HEAT project presents a reviewed and consolidated list of partners' key exploitable results, which can be seen in Table 2. Also a detail definition of this first version of KER exists as an internal document.

Table 8: List of Key Exploitable Results (KER)

Title	Lead	Final TRL	Innovative?	Joint/Indiv.
KER 1. Optimized AHT design and AHT control SW	TECNALIA	8	Yes	Joint
KER2. Modelling of Heat Upgrade Technologies applied to industries to quantify their technological performance	UPV	8	No	Joint
KER 3. Policy recommendations for high temperature heat pump technology scaling, acceptance and subsidies	EHPA	2	Yes	Individual
KER 4. Cost Reduction of the ThermBooster heat pump through modularization	SPH	9	Yes	Individual
KER 5. Software heat exchanger design and optimisation	VITO	?	Yes	Individual
KER 6. Implementation of Heat Upgrade Systems and assess. on their commissioning	FRAUN HOFER	9	Yes	Individual
KER 7. Maximize the Qpinch COP for maximum overall efficiency of the QTHT	QPINCH	7	No	Individual
KER 8. Large Scale High-Temperature Heat Pump with Centrifugal compressor	ENER	8	Yes	(Joint)
KER 9. Process and control design of AHT	TUB	7	Yes	Joint
KER 10. Business Models and Contractual Agreements (R12)	OST	?	Yes	Joint

5.2 Horizon Results Booster Service

The participation of PUSH2HEAT in the Horizon Results Booster initiative (HRB) has been explored since the beginning of 2023 (see previous version in deliverable D6.2). This is as an option that can help in the discussions on the exploitation strategies of the partners. PUSH2HEAT is an Innovation Action and there are strong expectations in exploitation, given also the fact that the market addressed by the project is starting to boost. Presentation of the HRB services to the consortium was made during the Antwerp Consortium Meeting (Apr 2024) and also reviewed in Valencia Consortium Meeting and Service 1-Module C “Improve existing exploitation strategy” was identified as the one from which more benefit can be obtained by PUSH2HEAT partners at this stage. Partners were consulted about this service and most of them indicated that they would advance by themselves with the support of the Exploitation part in WP6. Two partners showed interest in these services: VITO and ENERTIME. They will be the beneficiaries of the service.

A first contact with the HRB service was made and in the preparation meeting held with them, several inputs were requested to PUSH2HEAT partners in order to hold a session of diagnostics and recommendations to complete the key exploitable results of VITO and ENERTIME. According to

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia., the service will be delivered between September and October of the present year. Anyway, the service has to finish before the 7th of November, when the HRB initiative ends its activity.

Figure 6: Stages for the HRB Service 1 - Module C - Improve existing exploitation strategy

5. Conclusion

This is the second report on Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities (D6.4). The first report, produced in M12, is available [here](#). We will continue to produce additional reports at the end of each project year, specifically at M36 and M48, to provide a comprehensive overview of our progress.

In this report, we have outlined the activities conducted during the second year of the project. The efforts of the Push2Heat consortium have achieved notable results, particularly in improving our social media presence, expanding our outreach, and increasing engagement with stakeholders.

Over the past year, we have grown our online audience. Our LinkedIn following has increased to 640 followers, while our Twitter account has attracted 93 followers. Additionally, we organised three successful webinars in collaboration with sister projects and relevant organisations, attracting an average of 125 attendees and 186 registrants per event. These webinars have been instrumental to discuss the possibilities of the technologies of the project.

We have also increased our visibility by participating in 25 events this year, compared to the 20 events reported in the first year. To further disseminate our work, we produced a series of factsheets to highlight the achievements of Work Package 2 (WP2) and demonstrate the potential of the technologies being developed. Moreover, our promotional video has garnered over 6,000 views, effectively raising awareness of our project's goals and progress.

These accomplishments reflect our ongoing commitment to effectively communicating our project's value and ensuring that our stakeholders are well-informed and engaged.

